

HEYDAR ALIYEV IS THE NATIONAL LEADER OF THE AZERBAIJANI PEOPLE

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Abstract

Everyone lives the life given by God in a way, some for himself, some for his relatives and dear ones, and some for his nation, people, homeland and state. The national leader of the Azerbaijani people, Heydar Aliyev, dedicated his meaningful and rich life to his nation, people, homeland and state as a whole. This is exactly the secret of the great leader who loves his nation more than his life.

As a result of inexhaustible love for the nation, the birthday of Heydar Aliyev, the world-famous giant politician who played an unparalleled role in the fate of Azerbaijan with his exceptional services, the author of our independence and the architect of our modern state, who brought our country to the world community by putting our country on the path of rapid development, is celebrated every year in our republic, as well as far beyond its borders. is celebrated far and wide with great solemnity, the bright memory of our eternal leader is commemorated with deep respect.

Keywords: modernization, Azerbaijan, Karabakh, progress.

Heydar Aliyev is renowned as a prominent statesman and influential politician who played a pivotal role in the establishment and growth of independent Azerbaijan. Amidst challenging circumstances, Aliyev assumed power when the nation was on the brink of civil war and state collapse. With his leadership, Azerbaijan emerged from turmoil and witnessed remarkable progress, establishing itself as a respected member of the international community.

Aliyev's visionary approach encompassed oil contracts, internal stability, economic reforms, cultural development, and diplomatic efforts to bring about a ceasefire in the conflict with Armenia. Under his guidance, Azerbaijan experienced significant advancements in independent development, gaining worldwide recognition. Aliyev's unwavering dedication and wisdom propelled Azerbaijan toward prosperity. [2, 68]

The process of deep modernization of Azerbaijan's economy, political system, and public life commenced during Aliyev's leadership. As the leader of an independent nation, Aliyev prioritized the interests of his country. Notably, he facilitated "The Contract of the Century" on September 20, 1994, with 13 major oil companies, propelling Azerbaijan's oil strategy and positioning the country as a key player in global oil diplomacy. The influx of substantial investments, totaling around 20 billion dollars, enabled Azerbaijan to strengthen its spiritual power and overcome past challenges.

Aliyev's initiatives extended beyond economic growth. He hosted the international forum "Restoration of the Great Silk Road" in 1998, positioning Baku as a crucial hub in an international transit project. Through a pragmatic approach, Aliyev aimed to foster positive partnerships with various countries, including the United States, Russia, Europe, and Japan, to benefit Azerbaijan's people. [8, 73]

Under Aliyev's leadership, Azerbaijan became an active participant in international organizations and regional geopolitical processes. His contributions to the fight against terrorism, peace negotiations for the resolution of the Karabakh conflict, and the attraction of

foreign investments significantly bolstered Azerbaijan's position on the global stage.

Aliyev's commitment to Azerbaijan's progress was driven by his deep love for his homeland, his nation's well-being, and his aspiration for peace and harmony. He instilled a sense of patriotism and unity among Azerbaijanis, creating a national revival based on the ideology of Azerbaijanism. Aliyev's secular policies promoted stability and confronted extremist tendencies.

The liberation of Karabakh and the restoration of Azerbaijan's territorial integrity were among Aliyev's greatest aspirations. His foresight and determination laid the groundwork for the eventual resolution of the conflict, as Azerbaijan, under President Ilham Aliyev's leadership, drove out the occupiers and raised the national flag in Shusha, a significant milestone in reclaiming Azerbaijani lands. [9, 34-35]

Aliyev's name will forever be intertwined with Azerbaijan's history. His prosperous and progressive leadership, along with his commitment to regional stability, earned him sincere respect and influence worldwide. Through his wise and far-sighted policies, Azerbaijan emerged as a trusted and stable actor in foreign affairs, continually advancing socially and economically. Aliyev's legacy as a visionary leader of modern democratic Eurasia remains indelible.

Today, Heydar Aliyev lives on in the memory and hearts of the Azerbaijani people. His unwavering patriotism and dedication to Azerbaijanism have become an integral part of the nation's identity, shaping the era in which they live and ensuring a prosperous future.

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